

Studies on Addition Polymerization in Mixed Solvent-System Part-II. Chain Transfer of Water in Polymerization of Vinyl Monomers

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The role of water as a chain-transfer agent as well as its effect on the transferring capacity of the cosolvent in addition to polymerization of methyl methacrylate, ethyl methacrylate, isobutyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate, acrylonitrile, vinyl acetate and acrylamide in a mixed solvent system has been studied. Water has been found to have hardly any transfer with the growing polymer radical. The degree of polymerization is found to increase with increasing water concentration. This is explained on the basis that water is a non-solvent for most of the polymers except polyacrylamide and in all probability polymer radical seems to exist in a coiled state thereby reducing the rate of termination. In case of acrylamide where water is a solvent for the polymer, no perceptible transfer reaction with water has been observed.

In a previous communication¹ we have reported on the role of water as a chain transferring agent in the polymerization of methyl methacrylate. The present communication reports study on the effect of water in the polymerization of other vinyl monomers like acrylamide, acrylonitrile, ethyl methacrylate, isobutyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate and vinyl acetate. Mixed-solvent system was employed and *t*-butyl alcohol was selected as the cosolvent to keep the mixture of water and monomer in homogeneous phase.

EXPERIMENTAL

Purification of the Vinyl Monomers: Before working, stabilised methyl acrylate, methyl methacrylate, ethyl methacrylate and iso-butyl methacrylate, monomers were all washed with 2-5% caustic soda solution until free of stabilizer and then rendered free of alkali by repeated washing with distilled water and kept over fused calcium chloride. The dried monomers were then distilled under vacuum, the middle fractions being collected.

Vinyl acetate was purified by the method of Nozaki and Bartlett² with slight modification. Commercial sample was first distilled through a long fractionating column and the distillate was stored overnight over anhydrous sodium sulphate. It was then filtered and refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen with a little benzoyl peroxide catalyst. When the mixture became moderately polymerized, it was distilled finally in an atmosphere of nitrogen through a long fractionating column. The fraction boiling between 72.8°-73° was collected. During all these procedures great care was taken to exclude air or moisture in the system.

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2. P. D. Bartlett and K. Nozaki, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 136.

Acrylonitrile was purified by following the method of Bamford *et al.*³ The monomer was first washed with dilute sulphuric acid (1*M*) followed by washing with distilled water to remove the acid. It was then washed with sodium carbonate solution (5%) and finally with distilled water, to remove traces of sodium carbonate. The washed monomer was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride for 24 hrs. filtered and fractionally distilled. The middle fraction (B.P. 77°) was collected over anhydrous calcium chloride, and distilled in vacuum just before use. Acrylamide was repeatedly crystallised from chloroform

Purification of Solvents : The solvents used were analytical reagent grade. They were purified by the usual methods⁴, dried, and fractionally distilled before use.

Purification of Initiators : 2,2-azobisisobutyronitrile and 2-2-azobisisobutyroamide were thrice crystallized from methanol and water, respectively.

Polymerization Experiments : Polymerization experiments were as described in the previous paper¹.

Determination of the Degree of Polymerization : The degree of polymerization (\bar{P}_n) was determined by viscometric method for the relation

$$\bar{P}_n = K[\eta]^\alpha$$

where $[\eta]$ is the intrinsic viscosity of the solution, K and α are constants for each polymer system in the solvent mentioned in Table I. The values used in calculations in the present work are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Polymer	Solvent	Temp. °C	$K \times 10^{-3}$	α	Reference
Polymethyl methacrylate	Benzene	30	2.205	1.32	5
Polymethyl acrylate	Benzene	35	3.258	1.40	6
Polyethyl methacrylate	Methyl Ethyl Ketone	35	2.818	1.234	7
Polyisobutyl methacrylate	Methyl Ethyl Ketone	35	3.12	1.37	7
Polyvinyl acetate	Acetone	35	2.92	1.45	9
Polyacrylonitrile	Dimethyl Formamide	30	49.6	1.36	10
Polyacrylamide	Water	30	88.72	1.52	11

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RESULTS

In case of mixed solvent system, where two solvents S_1 and S_2 are employed, the equation for the degree of polymerization \bar{P}_n was reported¹² to be

$$1/\bar{P}_n = C_M + C_{S_1} \frac{[S_1]}{[M]} + C_{S_2} \frac{[S_2]}{[M]} + \frac{R_p \delta^2}{[M]^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

for thermal polymerization or for initiated system where $C_I \simeq 0$. C_M , C_{S_1} , C_{S_2} and C_I are chain transfer constants for monomer (M), solvent (S_1), solvent (S_2) and initiator (I) respectively, and δ is a constant ($= k_t^{1/2}/k_p$). Keeping the ratio $[S_1]/[M]$ constant (1 : 1 in present case) and varying the concentration of S_2 (water) we can write

$$\left(1/\bar{P}_n - \frac{R_p \delta^2}{[M]^2} \right) = C_M + C_{S_1} \frac{[S_1]}{[M]} + C_{S_2} \frac{[S_2]}{[M]} = \text{Constant} + C_{S_2} \frac{[S_2]}{[M]} \quad \dots (2)$$

In the present case tert-butyl alcohol was selected as the cosolvent (S_1) to keep the mixture of monomer and water (S_2) homogeneous. Under these conditions the slope of the plot $(1/\bar{P}_n - R_p \delta^2/[M]^2)$ against $[H_2O]/[M]$ would give the value of C_{H_2O} .

The polymerization of acrylamide was carried out using water soluble, 2,2-azobisisobutyroamidine (I) as initiator at constant initiator concentration. Under such conditions the rate of polymerization remaining constant, then Mayo's¹³ equation can be used.

$$1/\bar{P}_n = \text{constant} + C_{S_2} \frac{[S_2]}{[M]}$$

The results are given in Table I. Similar experiment was carried out with vinyl acetate using 2,2-azobisisobutyronitrile as initiator at 90° and the results are given in Table I.

The results of the thermal polymerization of methyl methacrylate, ethyl methacrylate and methylacrylate in solution (*t*-butyl alcohol : monomer = 1:1 by volume) with different amounts of water at 80.5° are given in Table II and results of AIBN initiated polymerization of methyl methacrylate, iso-butyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate and acrylonitrile in the presence of water are represented in Table III.

DISCUSSION

Since water is a non-solvent for poly(methyl methacrylate) we have chosen acrylamide for our work, poly-acrylamide being soluble in water. In the acrylamide-water system polymerization was carried out at different concentrations of water with 2,2-azobisisobutyroamidine as initiator, at constant initiator concentration. The degree of polymerization was found to be independent of water concentration and plot of $1/\bar{P}_n$ against $[H_2O]/[M]$ gave a straight line parallel to $[H_2O]/[M]$ axis, indicating that in this system water has no chain transfer.

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TABLE II

Effect of water on the degree of polymerization

Monomer	Initiator (I)	$[\text{H}_2\text{O}]/[\text{M}]$	$\frac{1}{\bar{P}_n} \times 10^5$	C_{water}
Acrylamide*	2,2' azobis- isobutyroamidino	35.21	1.18	~0
		45.01	1.13	
		50.72	1.13	
		60.36	1.13	
		71.98	1.14	
Vinyl Acetate**	2,2' azobis- isobutyronitrile	0.00	122.4	
		0.09	103.0	
		0.17	93.7	
		0.35	75.2	
		0.52	76.5	
		0.70	78.1	

* Temp. 80°. ** Temp. 90°. $[\text{I}]/[\text{M}]$ is kept constant.

TABLE III

Effect of water on the degree of polymerization in the thermal polymerization of Acrylic and Methacrylic esters at 80.5°

Monomer	$[\text{H}_2\text{O}]/[\text{M}]$	$\frac{1}{\bar{P}_n} \times 10^5$	$R_p \times 10^5$ moles l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	$\frac{1}{\bar{P}_n} - R_p \frac{\delta^2}{M^2} \times 10^5$
Methyl Methacrylate ¹	0.00	5.67	0.64	4.90
	0.01	5.42	1.22	4.20
	0.05	5.28	1.37	3.92
	0.11	5.11	1.40	3.72
	0.23	5.20	1.44	3.76
	0.46	5.41	1.53	3.69
Ethyl Methacrylate ²	0.00	6.74	1.53	4.05
	0.13	5.56	1.73	2.54
	0.27	5.57	1.89	2.28
	0.39	5.50	1.95	2.10
	0.55	5.45	1.90	2.06
	0.79	5.60	1.87	2.26
Methyl Acrylate ³	0.00	3.20	1.53	3.15
	0.08	1.97	1.73	1.87
	0.17	2.11	1.89	2.02
	0.34	1.92	1.95	1.83
	0.49	1.89	1.90	1.80
	0.67	1.91	1.87	1.81

 $\delta_1 = 5.23$ (ref. 15). $\delta_2 = 5.27$ (ref. 7). $\delta_3 = 0.82$ (ref. 14).

As observed in the case of methyl methacrylate¹ addition of small amounts of water did bring an increase in the average degree of polymerization (\bar{P}_n) in the polymerization of higher esters of methacrylic acid. As mentioned earlier the growing polymer radical exists as a coiled chain in the presence of water thereby hindering the usual bimolecular termination resulting in lowering on the value for k_t . This hindrance would be more pronounced as we go up the series due to the presence of bulky groups causing enough steric hindrance. According to Burnett *et al.*¹⁸ propagation rate constant (k_p) remains almost constant for the

TABLE IV

Effect of water on the D.P. (\bar{P}_n) in the polymerization of different monomers initiated by 2,2' azobisisobutyronitrile at 80.5°

Monomer	[H ₂ O]/[M]	$\frac{1}{\bar{P}_n} \times 10^5$	$R_p \times 10^5$ moles l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	$\frac{1}{\bar{P}_n} - R_p \frac{\delta^2}{M^2} \times 10^5$
Methyl Methacrylate ¹	0.00	23.42	11.50	8.95
	0.01	21.69	11.62	7.06
	0.04	20.25	11.73	6.09
	0.19	20.09	11.80	5.24
	0.24	18.84	11.92	4.84
	0.33	20.43	12.01	5.06
Isobutyl Methacrylate ⁴	0.00	19.63	11.32	4.07
	0.09	19.74	11.90	2.80
	0.32	18.76	11.78	2.59
	0.66	18.60	11.68	2.54
	0.73	19.30	12.08	2.70
	0.99	18.05	11.53	2.20
Methyl Acrylate ³	1.33	18.37	11.90	2.03
	0.00	14.10	30.70	13.42
	0.08	10.80	31.20	10.11
	0.17	9.28	31.80	8.58
	0.34	9.31	32.50	8.59
	0.50	9.14	32.00	8.43
Acrylonitrile ^{5*}	0.67	9.42	32.80	8.70
	0.84	8.96	32.00	8.25
	0.00	8.28	1.64	8.05
	0.11	9.07	3.35	7.81
	0.18	7.52	3.58	7.03
	0.22	6.62	3.48	6.14
	0.29	6.22	3.73	5.71
	0.55	6.35	3.62	5.85
	0.74	6.22	3.68	5.71

$$\delta_4 = 3.6 \text{ (ref. 7)}, \quad \delta_5 = 2.80 \text{ (ref. 17)}.$$

* Co-solvent employed dimethyl formamide.

series of the methacrylate esters. In such a situation the termination step is affected by such coiling and that the degree of this reduction in k_t is more and more pronounced as we go up the ester series, the resulting value of \bar{P}_n would be comparatively much higher compared to that of the lower esters. This means that $1/\bar{P}_n$ would show decreasing tendency, the tendency being more pronounced with the higher esters. From the experimental results the same behaviour might be noticed (Table III and Table IV). At a fixed concentration of water ($[\text{H}_2\text{O}]/[\text{M}]$) the $1/\bar{P}_n$ value decreases with increase in the bulkiness of the ester group. A somewhat similar trend may be expected in the case of methyl acrylate ($k_p = 1580$ at 25°) which has a higher value for k_p than methacrylates (262 at 25°).

This initial decrease in the value of $1/\bar{P}_n$ can be explained in the light of lowering in the rate of termination due to the existence of the polymer radical in a coiled state. The degree of this lowering would depend on the bulkiness of the ester group. In case of all the plots of $(1/\bar{P}_n - R_p \delta^2 / [M]^2)$ against $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]/[\text{M}]$ the intercept gives the value of $C_M + C_{S_1} [S_1]/[M]$, thereby showing that in the absence of water the normal bimolecular termination is effective.

The results of the polymerization of vinyl acetate and acrylonitrile in the presence of varying amounts of water show similar trend as observed with the methacrylic esters and methyl acrylate. From the same trend observed in all these monomers it can be safely concluded that the growing polymer chain behaves identically in all the cases, the chain remaining coiled due to the presence of a non-solvent like water. The degree of the coiling which in other words, the barrier to the termination reaction would depend on the amount of water present in the system. Finally the conclusion that water has hardly any transferring ability is applicable to all the monomers studied.

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